

An Open-Source Hardware-Software Framework for Algorithm Evaluation in Battery-Powered Embedded Systems

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Abstract

The design of algorithms for Battery Powered Embedded Systems (BPES) requires careful balancing between provided functionality and its impact on overall system lifetime, making energy efficiency one of the primary design challenges. Despite the importance of energy-aware design in such systems, there is a lack of unified hardware-software toolsets that simplify and systematize the development, analysis, and evaluation of BPES. This paper presents a unified hardware-software toolset that integrates real measurements, battery characterization, and embedded-system models to evaluate the impact of different algorithms on system energy consumption, while simplifying algorithm analysis and accelerating optimization prior to deployment on real BPES. To demonstrate the capabilities and practical relevance of the developed toolset, a representative use case, involving battery State of Charge (SoC) estimation algorithms commonly employed in BPES, was evaluated: Coulomb Counter (CC), an Extended Kalman Filter based on the Rint battery model (K0), and an Extended Kalman Filter based on the Dual Polarization battery model (K2). The results validate the proposed framework while illustrating characteristic effects of these techniques, such as error accumulation, feedback-based correction, and the impact of battery-model fidelity on estimation accuracy, thereby demonstrating its usefulness for energy-aware design and optimization of BPES.

Keywords: Embedded Systems; Batteries; State of Charge Estimation; Extended Kalman Filter; Coulomb Counter; Simulation framework;

1 Introduction

Battery Powered Embedded Systems (BPES) have become one of the most rapidly expanding areas of modern embedded systems. The continuous growth of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, wearable electronics, wireless sensor networks, portable medical devices, autonomous robotic systems, and battery powered industrial platforms has significantly increased the demand for highly energy-efficient embedded solutions. Unlike traditional computing systems, BPES are constrained by limited energy availability, making the maximization of operational lifetime a key design consideration.

In such systems, evaluation and optimization of embedded algorithms play a critical role in extending operational lifetime and improving overall system efficiency. Different implementations of the same algorithm may provide different energy-consumption profiles depending on computational complexity, memory usage, communication overhead, and peripheral utilization [1], [2]. This becomes particularly important in systems that utilize low-power optimization techniques such as duty cycling, where hardware components periodically alternate between active and low-power states to reduce average power consumption [3]. Therefore, accurate evaluation of algorithm behavior and its influence on energy consumption is essential for identifying implementations that provide the best trade-off between accuracy, computational requirements, and energy efficiency.

To address these challenges, this paper presents a unified hardware-software toolset for energy profiling, battery analysis, and evaluation of algorithms executed on BPES. The primary goal of the proposed toolset is to simplify the analysis and evaluation of algorithm design decisions and their impact on overall system energy consumption, while accelerating algorithm optimization prior to deployment on real BPES. The solution provides a uniform infrastructure that combines real energy

measurements generated during algorithm execution with various software-based analysis approaches. The hardware part includes a high-precision measurement subsystem and a programmable battery charging subsystem intended for battery characterization and testing. The software part consists of a backend infrastructure that enables implementation and execution of arbitrary algorithms intended for BPES, as well as a frontend application that provides an intuitive and user-friendly graphical interface for system configuration, monitoring, visualization, and analysis of collected data. Existing solutions typically focus on specific aspects of BPES development, such as energy profiling, battery characterization, model extraction, or SoC algorithm evaluation. In contrast, the proposed toolset combines these functionalities within a unified open-source workflow supported by real measurements. A comparative overview of representative solutions is presented in Table 1. As such, the developed toolset provides a practical framework for both academic research and industrial development of battery-powered embedded systems. Both the hardware and software components of the proposed toolset were developed by the authors and are released as open-source/open-hardware resources to support research and further development. The complete software source code is publicly available in the project repository [4], while the complete hardware design files and documentation are available in [5]. Both software and hardware are distributed under the MIT License, allowing unrestricted use, modification, and redistribution.

TABLE 1. OVERVIEW OF REPRESENTATIVE TOOLSET

Tool	Energy profiling	Battery Characterization	Battery Model Extraction	Measurement Hardware	Integrated GUI	Open Source
Eco [6]	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
Powerpack [7]	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No
Simplicity Studio [8]	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Simscape Battery [9]	Partial	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Our toolset	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Battery State of Charge (SoC) estimation algorithms are among the most critical components of modern BPES, as they directly influence energy management, system reliability, and operational lifetime [10]. The need for systematic analysis and evaluation of SoC estimation algorithms was one of the key motivations for the development of the proposed hardware-software toolset. Developed toolset should enable identification of algorithm variants that provide the optimal balance between estimation accuracy and energy efficiency for deployment on real embedded platforms [11]. Consequently, this paper presents a comparative analysis of three widely used SoC estimation approaches implemented and evaluated on a real embedded platform: the Coulomb Counting method (CC) [12], an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) based on a simple *Rint* battery model (K0), and an EKF based on a Dual Polarization battery model (K2) [11]. Using the proposed hardware-software framework, detailed energy profiling and algorithm evaluation are performed under realistic operating conditions to analyze the trade-offs between estimation accuracy, and overall impact of achieved operational time. The obtained results demonstrate that the proposed framework provides an effective infrastructure for development, validation, and optimization of energy-aware embedded algorithms, significantly simplifying the design of BPES for both industrial and academic applications. Because it is developed as an open-source project, it enables end users to continuously enhance and extend their capabilities, allowing the solution to be applied not only to the evaluation of battery SoC estimation algorithms but also to a wide range of other algorithms relevant to BPES.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the main hardware and software components of the developed toolset. Section 3 presents the considered use cases, including the implemented battery State of Charge estimation algorithms. Section 4 presents the experimental results and analysis obtained using the developed framework, while the final Section 5 provides concluding remarks and discusses the main contributions of this work.

2 Toolset components

The proposed toolset was designed as a unified combination of hardware and software components to provide a fully compatible and standardized environment for complete evaluation of algorithms intended for BPES. The primary motivation is the fact that reliable analysis of energy-constrained embedded applications cannot be achieved using isolated tools that address only individual parts of the evaluation process. Instead, the proposed framework enables different set of hardware and software tools that includes precise measurement of algorithm energy consumption, battery characterization and modeling, and comparative evaluation of different algorithmic approaches under identical operating conditions. Overall framework components are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall framework components and their connections

The primary role of hardware components is to characterize battery behavior, measure platform power consumption under different operating conditions, and determine the execution time of the evaluated algorithms on the target embedded platform. The collected data are subsequently used to populate the three key data structures of the simulation framework: the **Battery Parameters** table, which describes the electrical characteristics of the battery model; the **Platform Current** table, which captures the current consumption associated with different platform operating states; and the **Algorithm Duration** table, which contains execution-time measurements for the evaluated algorithms. The values stored in these tables represent the fundamental input data required for software-based evaluation of algorithm performance within BPES. The individual hardware and software components of the proposed framework, together with their roles in the parameter extraction and simulation processes, are described in the following sections.

2.1. Hardware components

The main hardware components are illustrated within Figure 2(a) while hardware implementation is presented within Figure 2(b). Developed hardware enables battery voltage and current measurement, programmable battery charging, generation of arbitrary current consumption waveforms, and implementation of all necessary protection mechanisms. This set of functionalities is essential for determining the parameters of battery electrical models and measuring embedded systems current consumption. Error: Reference source not found presents the hardware implementation of the measurement platform. Most of the system components are already introduced within [13].

(b)

Figure 2. Toolset hardware: (a) Block diagram [13]; (b) Hardware implementation

Voltage and current are measured using analog and digital circuitry, including operational and instrumentation amplifiers. In the current system version, a dual-channel A/D converter [14] performs simultaneous sampling on both differential input channels. The programmable charger is implemented using the BQ25180 integrated circuit [15], which supports charging of various lithium-based batteries. The programmable electronic load and its control logic represent one of the key components of the entire measurement platform for current consumption analysis and battery characterization. This subsystem enables the generation of arbitrary current consumption waveforms, including those required for battery parameter extraction as well as those that emulate the consumption profiles of real embedded computing systems. The combination of accurate voltage and current measurement with controlled generation of battery load currents constitutes the primary feature that enables systematic battery parameter extraction.

As the system operates with batteries that are sensitive to operating conditions, and capable of delivering currents up to 40 times greater than their nominal rated capacity, protection subsystem is one of the most important to ensure system robustness over time. The hardware protection circuitry includes overvoltage, undervoltage, and overcurrent protection mechanisms. Activation of any of these protections automatically generates a digital signal that is forwarded to the microcontroller-based control system, ensuring safe platform operation even under unexpected conditions or incorrectly defined experimental parameters. The main control logic of the hardware platform is implemented using the STM32H755ZIQ microcontroller [16]. The microcontroller integrates a wide range of peripherals, among which the most significant is the 100 Mbps Ethernet communication interface.

2.2. Software components

The developed simulation framework consists of two primary components: a simulation core and a graphical user interface. The simulation core incorporates software algorithms within a discrete-time simulation environment. It is also responsible for generating current profiles and maintaining synchronization with system-level activities. The graphical user interface provides an interactive environment for configuring simulation scenarios and visualizing system parameters in real time. Together, these components enable system-level analysis of the implemented algorithms under various operating conditions. The complete source code of the framework is available in the project's public repository [4].

2.2.1. Simulation core

To describe the interaction between software execution and hardware power dynamics, the backend is implemented as a modular sample-by-sample simulation environment. The overall architecture, interconnection signals, and functional modules are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Simulation framework software backend architecture

The **Battery Current Generator (BCG)** is the first execution block in the framework. It determines the effective battery load current based on execution state flags received from the Algorithm Block. The baseline current, I_{sys} , represents the system consumption excluding the evaluated algorithm. Depending on the execution state, the BCG either forwards the baseline current or adds the algorithm-related contribution. The resulting signal forms the total current profile applied to the battery model.

The current profile is then processed by the **Voltage Estimator**, which computes the corresponding battery terminal voltage. The estimator is based on the Dual Polarization (DP) battery model (shown in Figure 4), which captures both the dynamic and steady-state characteristics of battery voltage behavior [17]. The model uses two RC networks to represent fast and slow dynamic behavior, in addition to steady-state characteristics. After computation, the block generates a VE_{Done} signal indicating that valid voltage and current data are available.

Figure 4. Dual polarization battery model used within the Voltage Estimator block. Reproduced from [13] under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) License

The **Algorithm Block** represents the software execution layer of the framework. It executes user-defined algorithms and operates in three stages: **preprocessing**, **processing**, and **postprocessing**, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Algorithm execution stages

In embedded systems, algorithm execution can be further categorized based on its temporal interaction with baseline system tasks. Specifically, two execution modes are commonly distinguished: **Parallel (P)** and **Sequential (S)** execution. These flags define whether the algorithm executes concurrently with or independently from the regular system workload. Within example, illustrated in Figure 6, demonstrates how these modes are used to obtain different battery load current within system.

Figure 6. Utilization of Parallel and Sequential flag within simulation framework to determine battery load current

At the beginning of each cycle, the Algorithm Block receives inputs from the BCG and Voltage Estimator, which trigger the start of the **preprocessing stage**. This stage marks the beginning of each execution cycle, where the system determines the current execution state and selects the active operating mode. In this phase, the execution state is evaluated and one of the P, S, or N flags is generated. The selected flag is then latched and remains asserted throughout the execution of the algorithm, while being provided to the BCG. The **N flag** indicates that the algorithm is inactive and only the baseline system current is applied, while the P and S flags, defined in the previous paragraph, represent the two active operating modes of algorithm execution. This mechanism defines when the load model is active and ensures that the selected state is preserved throughout the execution cycle. Once the operating mode is determined, control moves to the **processing stage**, where the algorithm is executed according to the duration defined in the Algo Duration Table, while execution remains active as long as the latch condition is satisfied. The execution time is therefore directly coupled with the system-level timing constraints defined by the simulation framework. After processing is completed and the output data is available, the results are passed to the **postprocessing stage**. In this stage, synchronization with the rest of the simulator is handled using the *PPDone* signal together with timing information from the Algo Duration Table. The *PPDone* signal serves as a simple handshake, indicating that all operations for the

current cycle have finished. Finally, the postprocessing stage computes the energy consumption for a single execution cycle and updates the corresponding simulation outputs. Once the cycle is complete, all latch states and execution flags are reset, terminating the current execution phase and preparing the system for the next cycle.

In addition to deterministic modeling, a **Noise Generator** introduces stochastic disturbances into current and voltage measurements, reflecting sensor imperfections in real systems. This allows evaluation of SoC estimation robustness under realistic measurement uncertainty. The generated disturbance is modeled as zero-mean Gaussian white noise, where the variance is selected according to the experimentally characterized performance of the measurement hardware. This noise model was chosen because the dominant uncertainty sources in the employed analog front-end, ADC conversion process, and electronic measurement circuitry can be reasonably approximated as independent random processes whose aggregated effect follows a Gaussian distribution. Consequently, the generated noise provides a realistic representation of measurement uncertainty observed in real battery-powered embedded systems. For the current hardware platform, the noise variance was experimentally determined to be approximately $2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for both the voltage and current measurement channels. A reference SoC trajectory is also computed using an ideal Coulomb counting method, serving as ground truth for error analysis. The **SoCRef** module provides the basis for determining system operational time and estimating the SoC consumed by algorithm-related activities. It is based on a Coulomb counting approach. Although this method may introduce cumulative errors, they are minimized by executing the component at the maximum available update period. Consequently, its output can be used for both operational time estimation and reliable SoC evaluation.

All system-level signals generated within the simulation framework, including battery state variables, voltage measurements, current profiles, and algorithm-related outputs, are exposed as standard output variables of the Algorithm Block and associated modules. These signals are continuously available for logging and post-processing. A dedicated file parsing interface is used to store and organize simulation results, enabling structured recording of both electrical variables and algorithm outputs in a unified format for further analysis and visualization.

2.2.2. Graphical User Interface

While the simulation backend manages computational execution and analytical modeling, the graphical user interface (GUI) provides an integrated frontend environment for simulation control, visualization, and post-execution analysis. This GUI is built as plugin for existing OpenEPT GUI project [18], and its dashboard layout is illustrated in Figure 7. This layout consists of a toolbar, a dynamic plotting area, a log console, and a status bar.

Figure 7. Graphical user interface of the framework developed as part of the work presented in this paper.

The toolbar provides basic simulation controls, including start, stop, and pause operations, together with shortcuts for accessing dedicated configuration and reporting modules. Real-time electrical quantities, including battery current, system current, platform current, terminal voltage, and State of Charge (SoC), are visualized within the central plotting area, which supports interactive zooming, panning, and data export. Runtime activity is monitored through the log console displaying timestamped system messages, whereas the status bar indicates the active configuration and overall simulation progress. To support the complete simulation workflow, the GUI incorporates dedicated modules responsible for configuration and result analysis. These components are integrated into a separate layout illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Additional GUI windows: (a) Configuration; (b) Simulation results. Both presented GUI windows are developed as part of the work presented in this paper

The **Configuration Window**, illustrated in Figure 8 (a), serves as the primary environment for defining operational parameters. It enables plot visibility selection and loads critical input files, including battery profiles, input current waveforms, Open-Circuit Voltage (OCV) curves, and battery polynomial coefficients. The interface supports precise tuning of initial SoC conditions and SoC boundaries for simulation termination. Furthermore, it facilitates pipeline configuration by defining

specific algorithms, hardware platforms, battery types, and whether execution is driven periodically or via an external algorithm execution file containing predefined operational flags. Comprehensive post-execution analysis is provided through the **Simulation Log Window**, illustrated in Figure 8 (b). Upon simulation completion, this module aggregates detailed per-algorithm results, including electrical quantities, timing metrics, energy consumption statistics, and SoC performance indicators. Additionally, it reports standard statistical error metrics, such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), bias, etc. enabling a thorough quantitative assessment of algorithm accuracy and model performance. To evaluate estimation accuracy, MAE and RMSE are used as quantitative performance metrics. These metrics are defined as:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |e[i]|}{N}, \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N e[i]^2}{N}}. \quad (2)$$

where $e[i]$ is the discrete-time difference between the reference and estimated SoC values, and N is the number of evaluated samples.

3 Description and implementation of SoC algorithms

This section presents the use cases employed to validate and evaluate the proposed hardware-software framework using battery State of Charge (SoC) estimation algorithms executed on real BPES. The analysis focuses on the Coulomb Counting method and Extended Kalman Filter (EKF)-based approaches under different battery discharge profiles to investigate the trade-offs between estimation accuracy, computational complexity, and energy consumption (impact on overall operational time). The considered algorithms are described from both mathematical and implementation perspectives, including their associated battery models.

3.1. Algorithms descriptions

The fundamental method for battery State of Charge (SoC) estimation is the Coulomb Counting (CC) method, which is based on tracking the amount of transferred electric charge. The equation describing the operating principle of this method is:

$$SoC[k] = SoC[k-1] - \frac{I[k] \cdot T_E}{Q_{nom}}, \quad (3)$$

where $SoC[k]$ represents the current value of the battery State of Charge, $SoC[k-1]$ represents the previous SoC value, $I[k]$ denote the currently measured battery current, T_E is the execution period of the CC method, and Q_{nom} represents the nominal battery capacity [13], [19]. In analyses focused on the accuracy of battery State of Charge estimation methods, SoC values obtained using this method are most considered as reference values. In such analyses, the method is typically executed with a minimal sampling period selected to capture all variations in the battery current waveform. When configured in this manner, the CC method provides highly accurate reference SoC values that serve as the basis for quantifying the estimation error of other methods. Consequently, due to its simplicity, this method could initially appear to be an ideal solution for BPES. However, in practical implementations where real-time operation, energy efficiency, and processor-resource optimization are required, the application of this method becomes problematic in systems characterized by highly dynamic current-consumption profiles. To obtain SoC values within acceptable accuracy limits, the method must be executed within a very short period to avoid missing rapid variations in the consumption current, since the absence of a correction mechanism inevitably leads to error accumulation. On the other hand, even though the method itself is computationally simple, frequent execution prevents BPES from efficiently

implementing low-power operating modes, which are essential both for extending system operational lifetime and for reducing processor utilization. In addition, practical implementations suffer from several other limitations, including incorrect initial SoC estimation SoC_0 , deviations between nominal and actual battery capacity Q_{nom} (which may significantly differ from manufacturer-declared values), as well as errors caused by deviations in the execution period, all of which can substantially affect estimation accuracy [20].

The battery SoC estimation method based on the Extended Kalman Filter represents a common solution for implementation in battery-powered embedded systems. One of the key advantages of this approach is its flexibility regarding battery-model selection, execution-period configuration, and the possibility of adapting the implementation to the specific functional and system requirements of the target embedded platform. Furthermore, one of the most significant characteristics of the Extended Kalman Filter is its ability to regenerate and correct accumulated estimation errors during low-current operating conditions, which substantially improves long-term estimation stability, robustness, and reliability. Owing to these properties, EKF-based SoC estimation methods provide the potential to achieve an effective compromise between estimation accuracy, computational complexity, and the amount of energy consumed during algorithm execution across a broad range of BPES applications [21]. During operation, the EKF executes periodically and performs state estimation through prediction and correction phases based on system-state and measurement equations. The system can generally be represented using the following state (4) and measurement equations (5):

$$x[k] = Ax[k-1] + Bu[k-1] + \omega[k-1], \quad (4)$$

$$y[k] = Cx[k] + Du[k] + v[k]. \quad (5)$$

where x represents the system state vector, u represents the system input, the measurement vector, while A , B , C , and D denote the corresponding state-space matrices.

The computational complexity and estimation accuracy of the EKF are strongly influenced by the dimensions of the matrices involved in the estimation process, while these matrix dimensions are directly determined by the selected electrical battery model used for State of Charge estimation. This analysis is done within [11]. Consequently, the choice of battery model, together with the algorithm execution period, represents one of the key factors in balancing estimation accuracy against processor and memory resource utilization in BPES. The first is the *Rint* model, presented in Figure 9, which is computationally simpler and requires less computational power and memory resources, but provides limited estimation accuracy. The second is the *Dual Polarization* (DP) model based on a second-order equivalent circuit, which introduces higher computational complexity due to larger matrix dimensions, but enables significantly improved estimation accuracy across a broader range of embedded-system applications (illustrated in Figure 4).

Figure 9. Rint model Electrical battery models used in the analysis. Reproduced from [13] under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) License

3.2. Algorithms implementation

Before integrating the algorithms into the simulation framework, two preparatory steps were performed. First, the CC, K0, and K2 algorithms were implemented and executed on an STM32F476RG embedded platform to characterize their real execution-time and energy-consumption profiles. Using the measurement setup described in Section 2.1, the platform current consumption and algorithm execution durations were measured. The platform consumed approximately 10 mA in active mode, while the execution times of the CC, K0, and K2 algorithms were approximately 10 μ s, 1.5 ms, and 5

ms, respectively. Second, a battery-parameter extraction procedure was carried out to identify the parameters required by both battery models used in the evaluation. A detailed description of the extraction methodology and the obtained parameter values is provided in [13].

As described in the previous sections, the Algorithm Block provides a unified execution framework based on a structured preprocessing, processing, and postprocessing pipeline, combined with latch-based execution control and timing information provided by the Algo Duration Table. From a system-level perspective, all previously described framework modules are implemented as independent C++ classes, ensuring modularity, encapsulation, and a clear separation of concerns within the simulation architecture.

Each algorithm operates on a standardized input interface provided by the Algorithm Block, consisting of battery current (I_{Bat}), terminal battery voltage (V_{Bat}), and battery State of Charge (SoC_{Bat}). Within this framework, all estimation algorithms, including K0, K2, and Coulomb Counter (CC), are executed in a parallel execution mode (P-flag mode), where algorithm execution is temporally overlapped with the baseline system operation within each discrete-time simulation step. Although a sequential execution mode (S-flag) is also supported by the framework for configurational flexibility, it is not utilized for the currently implemented algorithms.

The SoC estimation generated by the selected algorithm is made available through a dedicated output variable of the Algorithm Block and exposed to the simulation environment. This ensures that all algorithms share a unified input/output structure and are evaluated under identical system-level conditions. From an integration perspective, all algorithms conform to a unified execution interface and are treated as interchangeable modules within the Algorithm Block. Each algorithm instance provides an initialization function that accepts a generic configuration structure, allowing the user to define arbitrary parameters, internal states, and algorithm-specific data without modifying the core simulation framework. This enables full flexibility in algorithm design while preserving compatibility with the overall execution environment.

The framework exposes predefined preprocessing, processing, and postprocessing callback functions that must be implemented by the user. If implemented, these hooks are invoked by the simulator within a global “preprocessing-processing-postprocessing” execution cycle executed at each simulation step. Within this cycle, system-level routines and user-defined functions are executed in a deterministic order defined by the framework. This behavior is not based on inheritance of execution semantics, but rather on controlled invocation within the framework-managed execution pipeline. The framework therefore abstracts scheduling and execution management through this global cycle, allowing the algorithm designer to focus exclusively on estimation logic.

4 Results

To validate the functionality of the proposed simulation framework and demonstrate its capability for evaluating real battery SoC estimation algorithms, two representative system-current profiles were developed. The first profile emulates the current consumption of an ultra-low-power embedded system (**LPS**), while the second represents a higher-power system (**HPS**) characterized by dynamic current variations. Together, these profiles enable the evaluation of algorithm behavior under significantly different operating conditions and power-consumption patterns. The corresponding current profiles are illustrated in Figure 10.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10. Battery current created in simulation: (a) - Low Power system case; (b) – High Power system case

The Low-Power System (LPS) operates in an inactive state for most of the observation period. Consequently, as shown in Figure 10(a), the low-power mode dominates most of the 12-hour simulation interval. Around the 1000 s mark, the system periodically wakes up for approximately 20 s, during which several algorithms are executed, resulting in short-term current variations visible in Figure 11(a). This type of system is particularly relevant because it illustrates the impact of periodic wake-up events, driven exclusively by SoC estimation activities, on the overall battery energy consumption. These wake-up events are especially noticeable during low-power operating periods, where current spikes associated with the 1 s execution interval of the SoC algorithm can be clearly observed. This is illustrated in Figure 11(b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 11. Battery current profile of the Low-Power System: (a) Segment corresponding to the active operating period of the system; (b) Enlarged view of periodic node wake-up events performed every 1 s for SoC estimation execution

The current waveforms shown in Figure 10 are generated by the Battery Current Generator and serve as inputs to the Voltage Estimator block. Using the generated current values and the SoC values provided by the Reference SoC block, which executes at the minimum system period of 10 ms, the Voltage Estimator computes the corresponding battery terminal voltage. The resulting voltage waveforms are presented in Figure 12.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. Battery voltage response of: (a) LPS; (b) HPS.

Based on the current and voltage waveforms presented in Figure 10 and Figure 12, it can be observed that the proposed framework provides detailed insight into the dynamic behavior of BPES. Such information is not only valuable for evaluating SoC estimation algorithms but can also be utilized to analyze other aspects of BPES design, including power-management strategies, capacity dimensioning, voltage-regulator selection, and operational lifetime estimation. Furthermore, the availability of practical current and voltage profiles enables the investigation of interactions between application workloads, characteristics of battery, and energy-management mechanisms under various operating conditions.

All results described until now are always generated independent of implemented algorithm and they provide useful base for further analysis of BPES. However, in this paper, primary focus was to demonstrate how developed simulation framework can be used to evaluate SoC estimation algorithms.

One of the primary parameters used to evaluate these algorithms is estimation error, which is presented in Figure 14, while raw estimation values are presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Raw SoC estimation values: (a) LPS - K0 vs CC; (b) HPS - K2 vs K0; where each algorithm execute with 1s period

(b)

Figure 14. SoC estimation error: (a) LPS - K0 vs CC; (b) HPS - K2 vs K0; where each algorithm executes with 1s period

For the LPS use case, the K0 and CC algorithms are compared since they are among the most employed SoC estimation methods in ultra-low-power embedded systems. The results presented in Figure 13(a) and Figure 14(a) clearly demonstrate the limitations of the CC method when it is not executed continuously at a sufficiently high sampling rate. In the considered scenario, both algorithms are executed periodically with a 1 s interval, and it can be observed that the estimation error of the CC method increases significantly over time. This behavior is not exclusively a consequence of the inherent characteristics of the Coulomb Counting algorithm but also results from the operating pattern of the low-power system shown in Figure 11(b). To perform an SoC estimation, the node must periodically wake up from its low-power state, which temporarily increases the system current consumption. Consequently, the current measured during the active interval is used within the Coulomb Counting integration process, even though the system spends most of its time in the low-power state. The resulting integration error, combined with measurement noise, accumulates over time and eventually leads to an estimation error approaching 25%. Although this issue could potentially be mitigated through additional compensation mechanisms, such as adjusting the integration interval or introducing correction logic, these approaches would increase computational cost and energy consumption, which is undesirable in low-power applications. In contrast, the results shown in Figures 13(a) and 14(a) highlight the ability of the Extended Kalman Filter based on simple Rint model (K0) to compensate for such errors. Unlike the CC method, K0 continuously incorporates voltage measurements through its measurement-update stage, comparing the measured terminal voltage with the estimated battery voltage and applying corrective feedback to the state estimate. This feedback mechanism enables the filter to suppress accumulated errors and maintain significantly higher estimation accuracy, particularly under low-current operating conditions. From an energy-consumption perspective, the use of K0 results in an estimated system operational lifetime of approximately 6351 h and 12 min, which is only about 2 h and 32 min shorter than the theoretical maximum lifetime. Although the CC algorithm imposes an even smaller computational overhead and therefore achieves a lifetime nearly identical to the theoretical maximum, its estimation error becomes unacceptably large. Consequently, the slight reduction in operational lifetime associated with K0 represents a favourable trade-off for the substantial improvement in SoC estimation accuracy. The obtained results are consistent with previous studies that have identified accumulated integration errors and sensitivity to current-measurement inaccuracies as major limitations of Coulomb Counting techniques, particularly when continuous sampling cannot be maintained. Similar observations have been reported in [20], [22], where Kalman-filter-based estimators demonstrated improved long-term stability due to periodic correction using voltage measurements [23].

For the HPS use case, characterized by highly dynamic load-current behavior, the analysis focuses on evaluating the benefits of the K2 estimator compared to K0. At first glance, the poor performance of K0 under these conditions may appear to be a consequence of an insufficient execution period. Therefore, it would be reasonable to assume that reducing the K0 execution period could significantly improve its performance. However, the obtained results demonstrate when the K0 execution period is reduced to the minimum supported value of 10 ms, and the filter parameters are carefully tuned, the estimation error remains outside the acceptable range, as illustrated in Figure 15. This indicates that the

primary limitation is not the execution frequency itself, but rather the inability of the underlying *Rint* battery model to accurately capture the transient voltage dynamics that dominate under highly dynamic load conditions. Most notably, the results show that K2, executed with a 1s period, achieves higher estimation accuracy compared to K0, executed with a 10 ms period, demonstrating that increased computational effort cannot compensate for the limitations of an inadequate battery model. This finding highlights the value of the proposed simulation framework, which enables quantitative evaluation of the trade-offs between model complexity, estimation accuracy, computational cost, and battery lifetime. The observed superiority of K2 under highly dynamic load conditions is also in agreement with previous studies showing that second-order RC battery models provide significantly better representation of transient voltage behavior than the simpler *Rint* model. Similar conclusions were reported [24], where increased model complexity resulted in improved estimation accuracy during rapidly varying load conditions

Figure 15. K2 vs K0 SoC estimation error where K0 execution period is 10ms and K2 execution period is 1s.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a hardware-software framework for the evaluation of battery State of Charge (SoC) estimation algorithms in BPES. The framework combines experimentally obtained battery parameters, platform current profiles, and algorithm execution-time measurements with a simulation environment capable of modeling battery behavior and system operation. As a result, it enables quantitative analysis of the trade-offs between estimation accuracy, computational complexity, energy consumption, and battery lifetime. The obtained results clearly demonstrate the limitations of the Coulomb Counting method in low-power embedded systems when SoC estimation is performed periodically. The observed error accumulation is not caused uniquely by measurement noise, but also by the periodic wake-up behavior of the system, which introduces additional integration errors over time. In contrast, the K0 Extended Kalman Filter effectively compensates for these errors through its voltage-feedback mechanism while introducing only a minor reduction in battery lifetime. For highly dynamic load profiles, the results show that K0 cannot achieve acceptable estimation accuracy even when executed at the minimum supported period. Conversely, the K2 estimator, based on the Dual Polarization battery model, maintains high estimation accuracy even at substantially longer execution periods, highlighting the importance of battery-model fidelity in BPES.

The developed tool set provides a valuable framework for both industrial and academic applications. Future work will focus on extending the framework with additional battery models, SoC and SoH estimation techniques, adaptive algorithm-selection mechanisms, and automated optimization procedures for identifying the most suitable estimation strategy under specific operating conditions. In addition, future versions of the framework will support real-time evaluation of battery management algorithms using live measurement data acquired directly from the OpenEPT hardware platform. Furthermore, its open-source nature and public availability encourage continuous development, community-driven improvements, and long-term extensibility, enabling the framework to evolve alongside emerging BPES technologies and research challenges.

6 References

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